

SOCIAL FORMATION OF YOUTH SPIRITUALITY PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS.

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O`spirinlar biror xodisani asoslagan, isbotlagan paytlarida uning muhim xususiyatlariga, birlamchi jihatlariga sinchkovlik bilan qarashi Darsliklardan o`qigan va o`qituvchidan eshitgan axborotlar, xabarlar va ma'lumotlarga ishonish va ulardan qanoat hosil qilish uchun faol harakat qilishlari. Tafakkurni oqilona yo`llar bilan o`stirish uchun favqulodda xolatlarda o`quvchining mazkur xususiyatini yomonlamay, balki uni rag`batlantirish to`g`risida so`z yuritilgan.

**Kalit so`zlar:** o`spirinlik davri, asosiy mazmun, o`qituvchi, o`quvchi, ijtimoiy xususiyat, axborotlar, xabarlar.

Annotation: In this article, teenagers should carefully look at its important features and primary aspects when they substantiate and prove a phenomenon. In order to develop thinking in a reasonable way, in emergency situations, it is said to stimulate this characteristic of the student, rather than to harm it.

Key words: adolescence, main content, teacher, student, social characteristics, information, messages.

Аннотация: В данной статье подросткам следует внимательно рассмотреть ее важные особенности и основные аспекты при обосновании и доказывании того или иного явления. Чтобы разумно развивать мышление, в экстренных ситуациях говорят стимулировать эту особенность ученика, а не вредить ей.

Ключевые слова: подростковый возраст, основное содержание, учитель, ученик, социальные характеристики, информация, сообщения.

First of all, the shift in self-awareness is clearly visible in adolescents. This score doesn't just mean growth. In a teenager, the desire to define his spiritual world, personal qualities, intelligence, abilities and opportunities increases. Students of this age have characteristics related to self-awareness. First, they will have the opportunity to more accurately assess their strengths and weaknesses, achievements and shortcomings, appropriate and inappropriate behavior. Although a teenager can fully imagine the features of his spirituality and psyche compared to a teenager, he allows shortcomings in their rational assessment. As a result, he overestimates his own characteristics, becomes arrogant, arrogant, and begins to behave abnormally towards the members of the class and pedagogic teams. Also, some teenagers underestimate their behavior, mental abilities and interests and tend to behave modestly. Another characteristic of a child in adolescence is a tendency to respect, feel and be proud of one's own worth, a sense of duty, a sense of conscience, reflected in complex interpersonal relationships. For example, a young man and a young girl understand sensitivity as understanding the difference between delicate and elegant situations, realizing the need, organizing help objectively, and doing it without affecting the individual's personality. A teenager evaluates his good intentions from the point of view of determining his place in the team, for example, "Am I suitable for my chosen specialty?" "Can I contribute to the development of society?" looks for answers to the questions. In order to create a clear idea of his own virtue in the student, the teacher should help him very skillfully and intelligently. Only then will deep respect and gratitude for the teacher and friends be awakened in the team. At the core of self-awareness, a desire to self-educate is born in the adolescent student, and finding ways to do this, there is a need to apply it to everyday life. In order to have a spiritual-psychological image that suits them, they look for a reasonable size, standard, complete, perfect symbol, model, high dream image that performs tasks. In teenagers, ideals are manifested in several forms. can be and reflected. For example, they dream of embodying high

qualities in themselves in the form of images of famous people, characters of artistic works. The content of these dreams may differ between teenage boys and girls. For example, girls often raise the image of a hard-working woman, attractive, feminine, elegant, chaste public figure, character of an artistic work to an ideal level. But some students are also inclined to imitate the negative qualities of historical figures, for example, a strong leader, a cunning spy, and others. The first teenagers have a serious attitude to spiritual qualities, the essence of moral standards. For example, they can deeply analyze concepts such as duty, conscience, pride, dignity, pride, responsibility, and honor. But not all. For the formation of moral and spiritual views, imaginations, pedagogues need to constantly search for creating a healthy environment and forming a stable personality. These include the careful organization of some controversial events, the discussion of some foreign films. It is an important task of the team of pedagogues to attack the bad behaviors and vices that occur in social life. In adolescents, the sense of coming of age gradually becomes a sense of determining one's place and expressing one's spiritual world. This point is reflected in the fact that he wants to be recognized as a special person.

At this age, the school environment, especially the class team, formal and informal peers have a strong influence on the formation of personal qualities. Under the influence of school and class groups, virtues such as tenacity, courage, patience, humility, discipline, honesty, and sympathy are improved, and vices such as selfishness, indifference, hypocrisy, arrogance, laziness, and ingratitude are eliminated faster. lives with the desire to be the leader, the first at work. But it does not always succeed. According to L.A. Umansky, a teenager should have the following qualities for this.

- a) moral qualities - sociability, sincerity, initiative, activity, hard work;
- b) voluntary qualities - perseverance, determination, independence, initiative, organization, discipline;

v) emotional qualities - cheerfulness, freshness, sense of humor and novelty, self-confidence, optimism, etc.

Another important characteristic of teenagers is the emergence of high-level friendship, camaraderie, brotherhood, and love.

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